

SLEEP DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Annotation

Objective: To study the structure and characteristics of sleep disorders in patients with arterial hypertension and to develop optimal treatment.

Key words: sleep disorder; sleep neurophysiology; brain structures, arterial hypertension, treatment correction.

Subject of the study.

An in-depth study of neurological symptoms will be conducted, scales for assessing the psychoemotional and cognitive status, neurophysiological (EEG, polysomnography) and neuroimaging (MRI of the brain, with centralization of the hippocampus and hypothalamic region, MRA of the cerebral vessels) studies will be used, ways of optimal correction of sleep disorders in hypertension will be developed depending on the obtained research results.

Arterial hypertension (AH) is one of the most common cardiovascular diseases. The overall prevalence of AH among the adult population is about 30-45% and has a constant tendency to increase. To date, a large number of well-tolerated, reliable and effective measures have been developed that are aimed at modifying lifestyle and using drugs to correct blood pressure and treat AH. However, blood pressure control remains inadequate worldwide, and is far from perfect in European countries. Despite the existing effective recommendations for the introduction of patients with AH, it remains the leader among modifiable causes of cardiovascular and general mortality worldwide. Therefore, there is a need for ongoing study of the problem of prevention and correction of arterial

hypertension. The development of AH is a complex process of interaction of a huge number of factors, both external and internal in the body. The unknown number of these factors, as well as the dynamism of many of them, do not currently allow creating a full-fledged concept of the development of this disease. However, with the emergence of new directions in medicine, a re-evaluation of known but previously poorly studied conditions, it became possible to come closer to understanding this complex process and subsequently develop methods that will help improve the quality of life of patients with this pathology.

Sleep is a complex set of brain processes that supports human physiological needs, part of the sleep-wake cycle, consisting of 8-hour night sleep and 16-hour daytime wakefulness, and controlled by a combination of two internal influences: sleep homeostasis and circadian rhythms. For many years, the problem of sleep disorders in healthy people and in patients with various diseases has been studied, but the true physiology of sleep in various diseases, how and for what reason the sleep structure changes in cerebrovascular pathology, what differentiating criteria are there when studying the sleep structure in patients with hypertension, whether the duration of the disease, the level of blood pressure increase, the stages of hypertension development affect the sleep structure, and how the cognitive function of the brain changes in these conditions. There are no specific methods for studying the structure of sleep that would assess the essence of its pathology, and criteria that could draw a clear line between the physiology and pathology of sleep. It has been proven worldwide that age predisposes to sleep disorders (at the age of 30-50 years - 5%, from 50 years and older, the number of people suffering from insomnia reaches 30%). This is due to a decrease in the total sleep time, more frequent awakenings at night, the presence of somatic pathology, the use of various medications. Stressful or tragic situations, shift work, change of time zones, changes in the altitude of residence can disrupt the sleep cycle and cause insomnia even in young people.

According to the National Institutes of Health (NIH), the incidence of sleep disorders in the US population is 6-10%, and among patients with neurological pathology it reaches 40-83%, depending on the form of the disease. One third of Americans report sleep disorders - from 20% to 40% of adults complain of sleep problems annually, of which about 17% consider it a serious condition.

Conclusion:

The study of the clinical structure of sleep disorders and its impact on the neurological aspects of symptom development in hypertension, the study of neurophysiological features of changes in sleep structure in hypertension in comparison with conditionally healthy people, a comparative analysis of neurophysiological, psychoemotional, cognitive changes in sleep disorders in patients with hypertension will allow developing ways to optimally correct dysomnia in hypertension.

References:

1. Bokebaev T.T., Kasenova A.S., Tazabekova G.S. The Impact of Cognitive Impairments on Sleep Quality in Young People // Bulletin of KazNMU. 2021;4:282-284
2. Bochkarev M.V., Korostovtseva L.S., Sviryaev Yu.V. Combination of Insomnia with Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome: A Practical Approach to Patient Management // Effective Pharmacotherapy. 2022;18(36):50-54.
3. Golenkov A.V. Sleep Disorders in Mental Disorders // IX All-Russian Scientific Practical Conference "Actual Problems of Somnology", November 18-19, 2014 - Neurology and Psychiatry. Special Issue "Sleep and Its Disorders - 2". 2014;22:22-28.

4. Ochilova D.O. Clinical and neurophysiological analysis of the features of sleep disorders in hypertension. // New day in medicine journal: 2 (64) 2024 290-293
5. Isaev R.I., Yakhno N.N. Sleep disorders in Alzheimer's disease. // Neurological journal. 2017; 22 (5): 228-36.

